

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Spatial Distribution of Groundwater Quality for Kuzhithuraiyar Sub basin of Kanyakumari District Using GIS

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 OPEN ACCESS

Received: 01/03/2026

Accepted: 13/03/2026

Published: 23/03/2026

Citation: Belfin Raj S , Srinivasan K , Monisha V , Chellathurai BR (2026) Spatial Distribution of Groundwater Quality for Kuzhithuraiyar Sub basin of Kanyakumari District Using GIS. Indian Journal of Science and Technology 19(10): 688-703. <https://doi.org/10.17485/IJST/v19i10.309>

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Funding: None

Competing Interests: None

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Published By Indian Society for Education and Environment ([iSee](https://www.isee.org/))

ISSN

Print: 0974-6846

Electronic: 0974-5645

Abstract

Objectives: To assess the spatial distribution of groundwater quality in the Kuzhithuraiyar Sub-Basin of Kanyakumari District, evaluate the extent of seawater intrusion and its impact on groundwater characteristics, examine the influence of urbanization and tourism on water quality deterioration, identify groundwater quality zones using suitable analytical and GIS techniques, and propose effective management strategies for sustainable utilization and continuous monitoring of groundwater resources in the region. **Method:** The study evaluates groundwater quality using key physico-chemical parameters, including Total Dissolved Solids (TDS), Turbidity, pH, Electrical Conductivity (EC), Alkalinity, Magnesium (Mg), Calcium (Ca), Total Hardness (TH), Chloride (Cl⁻), Sodium (Na), Potassium (K), Sulphate (SO₄²⁻), Fluoride (F⁻), and Nitrate (NO₃⁻) for the pre monsoon of 2023. Spatial analysis was carried out using Geographic Information System (GIS) techniques. The collected attribute data were integrated into the GIS environment using ArcGIS 9.1. The Inverse Distance Weighting (IDW) interpolation method was applied to generate spatial distribution maps for each parameter. These maps were then compared with standard permissible limits to assess groundwater quality variations across the Kuzhithuraiyar Sub-Basin. **Findings:** The study revealed significant spatial variability in groundwater quality across the study area, with severe deterioration observed in locations such as Paloor, Malavilai, Kannanoor, and Athencode. Total Dissolved Solids (566–2234 mg/L) and Total Hardness (107.396–965.034 mg/L) exceeded desirable limits in most sampling locations, indicating widespread mineralization and poor water quality. Elevated chloride concentrations (up to 671.96 mg/L) and electrical conductivity values (up to 1896.32 μ S/cm) suggest the influence of seawater intrusion in coastal zones. Nitrate levels reached 70 mg/L in several samples, surpassing the permissible limit and indicating contamination from anthropogenic activities. The spatial distribution maps clearly delineated contamination hotspots, emphasizing the uneven distribution of groundwater quality and the urgent need for targeted management and remediation strategies in critically affected regions. **Novelty:** This study demonstrates the effective integration of GIS and IDW interpolation techniques for groundwater quality assessment in coastal regions. The generation of spatial distribution maps for multiple water quality parameters offers a comprehensive understanding of contamination patterns. The approach provides a scientific basis for identifying critical zones and supports decision-making in groundwater management.

Keywords: Spatial Distribution; Groundwater Quality; Physico-Chemical Parameters; GIS; Inverse Distance Weighting (IDW)

1 Introduction

Groundwater is one of the most vital freshwater resources supporting agricultural production, industrial development, and domestic consumption worldwide. In coastal environments, aquifers are highly sensitive to both natural and anthropogenic disturbances, particularly excessive groundwater extraction, rapid urbanization, population growth, and climate variability. These factors collectively alter the natural hydraulic gradient and promote seawater intrusion, leading to groundwater salinization and deterioration of water quality in many coastal regions of the world^{(1), (2)}. Coastal groundwater systems are therefore increasingly threatened by salinity anomalies and hydrochemical transformations driven by declining groundwater levels and intensified human activities⁽³⁾.

India is one of the largest consumers of groundwater globally, where aquifers contribute nearly 60 % of irrigation demand and approximately 85 % of drinking water supply. However, uncontrolled groundwater abstraction and inadequate recharge management have resulted in widespread groundwater depletion and quality degradation, particularly in coastal states⁽⁴⁾. Among these challenges, seawater intrusion has emerged as a major environmental issue in several coastal aquifers, especially when groundwater levels fall below mean sea level, facilitating saline water ingress and modifying the hydrochemical composition of groundwater⁽⁵⁾.

Several hydrogeochemical investigations in the coastal regions of Tamil Nadu, including Chennai, Nagapattinam, Karaikal, and other deltaic areas, have reported elevated concentrations of chloride (Cl^-), sodium (Na^+), and electrical conductivity (EC), indicating mixing between freshwater and seawater. These studies demonstrate that marine influence, over-pumping, and land-use changes are the dominant factors controlling groundwater salinization in the region^{(6), (7)}. Hydrochemical and modeling studies conducted in coastal Tamil Nadu aquifers further confirm that seawater intrusion alters major ion chemistry and affects groundwater suitability for drinking and irrigation purposes⁽⁷⁾. Despite these findings, the spatial distribution and intensity of salinity intrusion often vary significantly across different coastal basins, requiring localized assessments to understand aquifer behavior.

Recent advances in hydrogeochemical analysis and geospatial technologies have significantly improved groundwater quality assessment and mapping. Geographic Information Systems (GIS) integrated with spatial interpolation techniques such as Inverse Distance Weighting (IDW) and kriging have been widely used to delineate contamination hotspots and identify spatial variability in groundwater quality parameters⁽⁸⁾. In addition, modern analytical techniques and hydrochemical indicators enable the identification of ionic interactions and trace-level contamination, allowing more precise characterization of salinization processes in coastal aquifers⁽⁹⁾.

Although numerous studies have examined groundwater salinity and seawater intrusion in the coastal regions of India and Tamil Nadu, many investigations are limited to a few hydrochemical parameters or short-term datasets. Comprehensive spatial analyses integrating multiple physicochemical parameters at the sub-basin scale remain relatively scarce^{(1), (10)}. The Kuzhithuraiyar Sub-Basin, located in Kanyakumari District of Tamil Nadu, represents a vulnerable coastal aquifer system experiencing increasing groundwater stress due to urbanization, tourism development, and intensive groundwater extraction. While earlier studies have reported indications of salinity intrusion and groundwater quality deterioration in parts of the district, detailed GIS-based spatial mapping of major hydrochemical parameters and salinity indicators across the entire sub-basin is still limited.

The motivation of this research is to evaluate groundwater quality and identify factors influencing its deterioration in the Kuzhithuraiyar Sub-Basin in the coastal region of Kanyakumari District, Tamil Nadu, India. Coastal aquifers are vulnerable to salinization due to seawater intrusion, rapid urbanization, tourism activities, and excessive groundwater extraction. These pressures have affected groundwater availability and suitability for drinking, agriculture, and domestic uses, highlighting the need to assess groundwater quality and support sustainable coastal aquifer management.

Therefore, the present study aims to assess groundwater quality in the Kuzhithuraiyar Sub-Basin using integrated hydrochemical and GIS approaches. Key parameters analyzed include Total Dissolved Solids (TDS), Turbidity, pH, Electrical Conductivity (EC), Alkalinity, Calcium (Ca^{2+}), Magnesium (Mg^{2+}), Sodium (Na^+), Potassium (K^+), Chloride (Cl^-), Sulphate (SO_4^{2-}), Fluoride (F^-), Nitrate (NO_3^-), and Total Hardness (TH). The study seeks to (i) evaluate spatial variability of groundwater quality parameters, (ii) identify zones affected by seawater intrusion, and (iii) provide scientific input for sustainable groundwater management in a stressed coastal aquifer system.

2 Methodology

2.1 Study Area

The present investigation focuses on the Kuzhithuraiyar sub basin, mainly covers a surface area of 351.564 km². Geographically, the sub-basin extends between 8°11' and 8°26' North latitude and 77°05' and 77°23' East longitude. It lies entirely within the administrative boundaries of Kanyakumari District, Tamil Nadu, and forms part of the larger Kodayar basin. This basin holds the highest population density in the state, with about 2230 persons per km², exerting considerable pressure on local water resources⁽¹¹⁾. This region is climatically distinct, being the sole area in Tamil Nadu to receive substantial rainfall from both the northeast monsoon (October to December) and southwest monsoon (June to September). The Kodayar basin, the district's second largest sub basin, features the Kuzhithuraiyar River as its main drainage channel. Beginning at approximately 1725 meters above sea level which is near the Pothigai Hills on the southwestern slopes of the Western Ghats, the river travels west and ultimately empties into the Arabian Sea near Thengapattinam, making it the only river from Tamil Nadu to reach this sea. The river system is further strengthened by several tributaries—including the Kodayar, Kallar, Kalikesanar, and Chittar—that join its flow after originating from various catchments across the Western Ghats. The basin is further supported by three major reservoirs—Kodayar, Pechiparai, and Perunchani—located at elevations of approximately 1816 m, 131 m, and 100 m, respectively. Rainfall during the monsoon seasons serves as the primary source of groundwater recharge, making the region's hydrological balance highly dependent on seasonal precipitation.

2.2 Materials and Methods

Recent study was implemented in the Kuzhithuraiyar Sub-Basin, located in Kanyakumari District, Tamil Nadu. Totally 34 groundwater samples (Table 1) were systematically assemble from different locations within the sub-basin in the year 2023 (Pre monsoon) to evaluate the physicochemical characteristics and determine their suitability for drinking purposes. Survey of India (SOI) toposheets (58H/2, 58H/3, 58H/4, 58H/6, 58H/7, and 58H/8) at a value scale of 1:50,000 were used as the base reference. These toposheets were scanned, geo-referenced, and subsequently imported into the GIS environment. After geo-referencing, a geo-database was developed, and the taluk boundary of the study area was digitized for further spatial analysis. A total of 14 physicochemical measurable factor were analyzed from the collected groundwater samples. The groundwater quality analysis included parameters such as Electrical Conductivity (EC), Turbidity, pH Total Dissolved Solids (TDS), Alkalinity, Potassium (K⁺), Magnesium (Mg²⁺), Sulphate (SO₄²⁻), Calcium (Ca²⁺), Total Hardness (TH), Sodium (Na⁺), Chloride (Cl⁻), Fluoride (F⁻), and Nitrate (NO₃⁻). The analysis followed standard procedures recommended by the American Public Health Association⁽¹²⁾,⁽¹³⁾,⁽¹⁴⁾. The suitability of groundwater for drinking purposes was evaluated by comparing the measured physicochemical parameters with the drinking water quality standards recommended by the Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS) under IS 10500:2012. All collected field and laboratory data were stored in a spatial database within ArcGIS software (version 10.1). To assess the spatial variability of groundwater parameters for quality checking, the Inverse Distance Weighting (IDW) interpolation method was implemented. IDW assumes that the degree of spatial correlation between sample points decreases with distance, and that closer points exert a greater influence on interpolation than distant ones. A mathematical weighting function was applied to the specified number of sample points within a defined search radius to estimate groundwater quality values for unsampled locations across the study area. The interpolated values of each parameter were represented in the form of spatial distribution maps, providing a visual interpretation of groundwater quality variation across the Kuzhithuraiyar Sub-Basin and compare with Permissible limit. These maps were further used to identify critical zones and appraise the appropriateness of groundwater for drinking purposes.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Turbidity

Turbidity values in 2023 ranged from 1 to 6 NTU, indicating spatial variability from very low to very high classes across the basin (Figure 1). Samples S3 and S29 exceeded the permissible limit of 5 NTU prescribed by IS 10500:2012 of the Bureau of Indian Standards. Elevated turbidity generally reflects suspended particulates, colloidal clay, and surface runoff infiltration, particularly during monsoon recharge. Similar turbidity exceedances were reported in coastal Tamil Nadu aquifers, where seasonal recharge enhanced sediment transport⁽¹⁵⁾. Compared with recent hydrochemical investigations in South Indian coastal basins⁽¹⁶⁾, the present study shows localized rather than widespread turbidity contamination. The limited spatial extent of very high turbidity zones suggests that the issue is site-specific rather than basin-wide. However, persistent turbidity may reduce disinfection efficiency and affect aesthetic quality, warranting filtration-based treatment in affected habitations (Table 2).

Table 1. Groundwater Sampling Locations

Sample No.	Location	Latitude	Longitude
S 1	Paloor	8° 14.63' N	77° 14.05' E
S2	Thozhichel	8° 13.41' N	77° 13.57' E
S 3	Alanchy	8° 11.97' N	77° 13.62' E
S 4	Hellen Nager	8° 12.61' N	77° 12.19' E
S 5	Thengapattnam	8° 14.33' N	77° 10.87' E
S 6	Painkulam	8° 16.34' N	77° 10.22' E
S 7	Kappukadu	8° 17.71' N	77° 12.00' E
S 8	ST Mankad	8° 17.61' N	77° 10.14' E
S 9	Valanoor	8° 17.98' N	77° 08.29' E
S 10	Chinnathurai	8° 16.05' N	77° 08.58' E
S 11	Methummal	8° 19.17' N	77° 08.40' E
S 12	Mariagri	8° 19.37' N	77° 09.90' E
S 13	Thiruthuvapuram	8° 19.39' N	77° 11.63' E
S 14	Vilazari	8° 19.26' N	77° 13.37' E
S 15	Marthandam	8° 17.64' N	77° 13.97' E
S 16	Payanam	8° 18.30' N	77° 14.49' E
S 17	Attoor	8° 19.44' N	77° 15.46' E
S 18	Kadamacode	8° 20.55' N	77° 13.61' E
S 19	Nullicadu	8° 20.76' N	77° 12.08' E
S 20	Malaicode	8° 22.65' N	77° 11.97' E
S 21	Palukal	8° 22.57' N	77° 10.08' E
S 22	Malavilai	8° 20.92' N	77° 17.86' E
S 23	Eanchacode	8° 21.14' N	77° 19.08' E
S 24	Ponmanai	8° 21.04' N	77° 20.26' E
S 25	Valiattumugham	8° 19.41' N	77° 18.91' E
S 26	Kannanoor	8° 17.39' N	77° 17.17' E
S 27	Vizhunthayambalam	8° 14.71' N	77° 12.02' E
S 28	Chadayankuzhi	8° 16.22' N	77° 12.13' E
S 29	Athencode	8° 18.38' N	77° 10.76' E
S 30	Chemmathal	8° 16.33' N	77° 13.39' E
S 31	Devicode	8° 23.89' N	77° 11.78' E
S 32	Vellachiparai	8° 25.88' N	77° 12.27' E
S 33	Muthalar	8° 19.52' N	77° 17.21' E
S 34	Perunchilambu	8° 17.63' N	77° 21.12' E

Although groundwater generally has low turbidity due to natural filtration through soil and rock strata, elevated turbidity observed at two sampling locations may be associated with the presence of fine suspended particles, clay or silt infiltration, disturbance during groundwater pumping, and local geological conditions. In addition, anthropogenic activities and the possible infiltration of surface runoff during rainfall may also contribute to increased turbidity in these locations.

3.2 pH

The pH ranged from 5.3 to 8.45 in 2023, with samples S3, S11, S17, and S21 falling below the lower permissible limit (6.5) recommended by the Bureau of Indian Standards (²). Acidic groundwater conditions may arise from silicate weathering, organic matter oxidation, or anthropogenic influences. Comparable acidic trends have been documented in lateritic coastal terrains of southern India (¹⁷). In contrast, inland crystalline aquifers typically exhibit alkaline dominance due to carbonate dissolution (¹⁸). The predominance of neutral to slightly alkaline pH over most of the basin indicates stable hydrochemical buffering, while localized acidity may enhance metal mobility and corrosion potential. Relative to recent studies in peninsular

Fig 1. Spatial Distribution Map of Turbidity

Table 2. Spatial Variability of Turbidity Across the Kuzhithuraiyar Sub-Basin

Description	Area (Km ²)
Very Low	62.725
Low	116.33
Moderate	130.887
High	34.57
Very High	7.002558

India, the basin demonstrates moderate pH variability, emphasizing the influence of lithology and recharge dynamics. Corrective lime dosing or blending strategies may be required in acidic pockets (Table 3).

Table 3. Spatial Variability of pH Across Kuzhithuraiyar Sub Basin

Description	Area (Km ²)
Very Low	13.35
Low	47.12
Moderate	171.82
High	48.33
Very High	70.89

3.2 Electrical Conductivity (EC)

EC values varied between 365 and 1896.32 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ in 2023. Although the maximum value remained below the BIS threshold of 2500 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, several samples (³, Table 4) showed elevated salinity signatures. Increased EC in coastal aquifers is commonly associated with seawater intrusion and mineral dissolution⁽¹⁹⁾. Compared to recent coastal aquifer studies in western and southern India⁽²⁰⁾, EC levels in the present basin indicate moderate salinization rather than advanced marine intrusion. The dominance of low-to-moderate EC zones suggests controlled hydrochemical evolution; however, continued groundwater abstraction could accelerate ionic enrichment. EC correlates strongly with TDS, indicating that salinity is primarily geogenic

Fig 2. Spatial Distribution Map of pH

with possible anthropogenic contributions. Sustainable groundwater management and artificial recharge interventions are recommended to prevent long-term salinity escalation.

Fig 3. Spatial Distribution Map of EC

Table 4. Spatial Distribution value of EC Across the Kuzhithuraiyar Sub-Basin

Description	Area (Km2)
Very Low	105.313
Low	143.7359
Moderate	88.741
High	11.8588
Very High	1.864604

3.3 Total Dissolved Solids (TDS)

TDS concentrations ranged from 566 to 2234 mg/L, with all samples exceeding the desirable limit (500 mg/L) and some surpassing the permissible limit (2000 mg/L) of IS 10500:2012. Elevated TDS reflects prolonged water-rock interaction, evaporative concentration, and possible seawater mixing. Similar high TDS trends were reported in coastal aquifers of Tamil Nadu and Andhra Pradesh (21). Compared with inland hard-rock aquifers (22), the present basin exhibits relatively higher mineralization, highlighting coastal vulnerability. Persistently elevated TDS can impair taste and limit suitability for drinking and irrigation (4), Table 5). The spatial dominance of moderate TDS zones suggests progressive hydrochemical evolution rather than abrupt contamination. Desalination or blending with low-TDS sources may be required in severely affected locations.

Fig 4. Spatial Distribution of TDS Map

Table 5. Spatial Distribution of TDS Across the Kuzhithuraiyar Sub-Basin

Description	Area (Km2)
Very Low	49.513
Low	193.35
Moderate	87.39
High	13.81
Very High	2.4502

3.4 Alkalinity

Alkalinity values ranged from 24 to 107 mg/L, well within the acceptable limit (200 mg/L) set by the Bureau of Indian Standards. These values indicate adequate buffering capacity and stable carbonate equilibrium ⁽⁵⁾, Table 6). Comparable studies in south Indian aquifers reported similar moderate alkalinity despite elevated TDS ⁽²³⁾. Unlike limestone-dominated terrains where alkalinity often exceeds 200 mg/L, the present basin reflects silicate-weathering dominance. The overall compliance suggests minimal risk related to bicarbonate alkalinity. Continuous monitoring is nevertheless essential to track long-term geochemical evolution.

Fig 5. Spatial Distribution Alkalinity Map

Table 6. Spatial Distribution value of Alkalinity Across the Kuzhithuraiyar Sub-Basin

Description	Area (Km2)
Very Low	41.885
Low	102.33
Moderate	149.952
High	52.113
Very High	5.2315

3.5 Calcium (Ca)

Calcium concentrations ranged from 32.49 to 330.29 mg/L, with multiple samples exceeding the permissible limit (75 mg/L desirable; 200 mg/L permissible as per BIS). Elevated Ca is attributed to plagioclase weathering and ion exchange processes ⁽⁶⁾, Table 7). Similar Ca enrichment in coastal aquifers was documented by recent hydrogeochemical studies in Tamil Nadu ⁽¹⁶⁾. Compared with crystalline aquifers of central India ⁽²²⁾, the present basin shows higher maximum Ca values, suggesting intensified mineral dissolution. Elevated calcium contributes significantly to total hardness. Localized softening treatment may be necessary in highly mineralized pockets.

3.6 Magnesium (Mg)

Magnesium values ranged from 6.379 to 93.57 mg/L, with exceedances in select samples. The desirable limit (30 mg/L) was surpassed in some locations, though most remained within permissible limits (100 mg/L) ⁽⁷⁾, Table 8). Comparable Mg

Fig 6. Spatial Distribution Map of Calcium monsoon

Table 7. Spatial Variability of Ca Across Kuzhithuraiyar Sub-Basin

Description	Area (Km2)
Very Low	106.379
Low	174.621
Moderate	64.034
High	4.528
Very High	1.9498

variability was observed in coastal sedimentary aquifers influenced by cation exchange⁽²¹⁾. Compared to inland hard-rock terrains⁽¹⁸⁾, Mg levels here reflect moderate geochemical mobility. Elevated Mg, along with Ca, contributes to hardness and scaling potential. Regular monitoring is recommended.

Table 8. Spatial Distribution Variability of Mg Across the Kuzhithuraiyar Sub-Basin

Description	Area (Km2)
Very Low	42.353
Low	194.42
Moderate	84.12
High	25.55
Very High	5.07

3.7 Total Hardness (TH)

TH ranged from 107.396 to 965.034 mg/L as CaCO₃, with all samples exceeding the desirable limit (200 mg/L). Such high hardness reflects cumulative Ca and Mg enrichment⁽⁸⁾, Table 9). Similar hardness dominance has been reported in coastal Tamil Nadu aquifers under marine influence⁽¹⁹⁾. Compared with other Indian crystalline terrains⁽²²⁾, the maximum hardness here is substantially higher, indicating advanced mineralization. Hard water may cause scaling and domestic inconvenience, necessitating softening techniques in highly affected zones.

Fig 7. Spatial Distribution Map of Mg

Fig 8. Spatial Distribution of Th Map

Table 9. Spatial Distribution of TH Across the Kuzhithuraiyar Sub-Basin

Description	Area (Km2)
Very Low	45.198
Low	198.53
Moderate	89.138
High	16.21
Very High	2.439

3.8 Sodium (Na)

Sodium concentrations ranged from 47 to 168 mg/L and remained within desirable limits (200 mg/L) (⁹), Table 10). Controlled Na levels suggest limited cation exchange and moderate saline intrusion compared to severely affected coastal basins(²⁰). Relative to arid western Indian aquifers where Na dominance is common(¹⁹), the basin shows balanced alkali metal distribution. Sodium hazard for drinking and irrigation appears minimal.

Fig 9. Spatial Distribution Map of Sodium

Table 10. Spatial Distribution of Sodium Across the Kuzhithuraiyar Sub-Basin

Description	Area (Km2)
Very Low	95.798
Low	205.866
Moderate	17.42
High	21.84
Very High	10.59

3.9 Potassium (K)

Potassium ranged from 7.62 to 35.62 mg/L, with widespread exceedances of the desirable limit. Elevated K may be linked to agricultural return flow and fertilizer application (¹⁰), Table 11). Similar anthropogenic K enrichment has been reported in intensively cultivated South Indian basins(²¹). Compared with natural background levels in hard-rock aquifers(¹⁸), the values indicate external inputs. Sustainable agricultural practices are recommended.

3.10 Sulphate (SO₄)

Sulphate values (7.7–67.7 mg/L) remained well below the permissible limit (200 mg/L desirable; 400 mg/L permissible) (¹¹), Table 12). Comparable low sulphate dominance was reported in silicate-dominated terrains(²³). Unlike gypsum-rich aquifers, sulphate here reflects minimal evaporite dissolution. The parameter does not pose a health concern.

Fig 10. Spatial Distribution of Pottasium Map

Table 11. Spatial Variability of K Across the Kuzhithuraiyar Sub-Basin

Description	Area (Km2)
Very Low	67.637
Low	58.282
Moderate	196.937
High	24.41
Very High	4.25

Fig 11. Spatial Distribution of Sulphate Map

Table 12. Spatial Distribution of Sulphate Across the Kuzhithuraiyar Sub-Basin

Description	Area (Km2)
Very Low	81.9
Low	217.15
Moderate	41.2
High	8.87
Very High	2.39

3.11 Chloride (Cl)

Chloride ranged from 110.5 to 671.96 mg/L, with several samples exceeding the desirable limit (250 mg/L) (¹²), Table 13). Elevated chloride is a key indicator of seawater intrusion (¹⁹). Compared with recent coastal investigations (²⁰), the maximum chloride concentration suggests localized marine mixing. Long-term abstraction control is essential to prevent further salinity ingress.

Fig 12. Spatial Distribution Map of Cl

Table 13. Spatial Distribution of Chloride Across the Kuzhithuraiyar Sub-Basin

Description	Area (Km2)
Very Low	159.64
Low	97.895
Moderate	81.99
High	9.749
Very Heigh	2.2375

3.12 Fluoride (Fl)

Fluoride ranged from 0.43 to 1.42 mg/L. While some samples exceeded the desirable limit (1.0 mg/L), all remained below the permissible threshold (1.5 mg/L) recommended by the World Health Organization and BIS (¹³), Table 14). Comparable moderate fluoride enrichment was reported in peninsular India due to fluorapatite weathering (²²). Preventive monitoring is advisable.

Fig 13. Spatial Distribution of FI Map

Table 14. Spatial Distribution of FI Across the Kuzhithuraiyar Sub-Basin

Description	Area (Km2)
Very Low	47.233
Low	136.3627
Moderate	106.752
High	38.372
Very High	22.791

3.13 Nitrate (NO3)

Nitrate ranged from 23 to 70 mg/L, with several samples exceeding the 45 mg/L limit (no relaxation permitted under BIS standards). Elevated nitrate is typically linked to agricultural runoff and domestic wastewater infiltration (¹⁵, Table 15). Similar nitrate contamination patterns have been observed in South Indian coastal aquifers (²¹). Compared with pristine crystalline aquifers (¹⁸), the higher concentrations here indicate anthropogenic impact. Immediate mitigation and nutrient management are recommended.

Table 15. Spatial variability of Nitrate Across the Kuzhithuraiyar Sub-Basin

Description	Area (Km2)
Very Low	36.8
Low	169.679
Moderate	84.389
High	32.049
Very High	28.597

4 Conclusion

The present study provides a comprehensive evaluation of groundwater quality in the Kuzhithuraiyar Sub-Basin of Kanyakumari District through the integration of hydrochemical analysis and GIS-based spatial mapping. The analysis of fourteen physicochemical parameters revealed considerable spatial variability in groundwater characteristics, reflecting the combined influence of geological processes, seawater intrusion, and anthropogenic activities. Elevated values of Total Dissolved

Fig 14. Spatial Distribution Map of Nitrate concentration

Solids (566–2234 mg/L) and Total Hardness (107.396–965.034 mg/L) across most sampling locations indicate significant mineralization of groundwater, which reduces its suitability for drinking without treatment. Similarly, higher concentrations of chloride (up to 671.96 mg/L) and increased electrical conductivity values highlight the influence of saline water mixing in the coastal zones, suggesting progressive seawater intrusion into the aquifer system.

The presence of nitrate concentrations reaching 70 mg/L in several sampling locations further indicates contamination associated with human activities such as agricultural runoff, improper waste disposal, and domestic wastewater infiltration. Although parameters such as sodium, sulphate, alkalinity, and fluoride generally remained within permissible limits, the elevated levels of calcium, magnesium, turbidity, and potassium in certain locations demonstrate localized water quality deterioration. The spatial interpolation maps generated using the IDW technique clearly delineated contamination hotspots, particularly in Paloor, Malavilai, Kannanoor, and Athencode, where multiple parameters simultaneously exceeded recommended standards.

This research directly aligns with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), specifically supporting SDG 6: Clean Water and Sanitation. By assessing 14 physicochemical parameters against BIS (IS 10500:2012) standards, this study identifies critical areas where groundwater exceeds permissible limits for TDS, Total Hardness, and Nitrate. These findings provide a scientific basis for Target 6.1 (achieving universal access to safe drinking water) and Target 6.3 (improving water quality by reducing pollution and identifying contamination hotspots). Furthermore, the identification of seawater intrusion through elevated chloride and EC levels supports Target 6.6 regarding the protection of water-related ecosystems. Finally, by highlighting the health risks of elevated nitrate levels, the study contributes to SDG 3: Good Health and Well-being by promoting the prevention of waterborne health issues in the coastal population.

The results emphasize that groundwater quality degradation in the Kuzhithuraiyar Sub-Basin is not uniform but occurs in distinct zones influenced by coastal proximity, hydrogeological conditions, and land-use practices. The study demonstrates the effectiveness of integrating hydrochemical analysis with GIS-based spatial techniques for identifying vulnerable groundwater zones in coastal aquifer systems. Such spatial assessments are essential for developing targeted management strategies and improving groundwater resource planning.

To ensure long-term sustainability of groundwater resources in the basin, it is essential to implement controlled groundwater extraction, promote artificial recharge structures, regulate agricultural chemical usage, and strengthen wastewater management practices. Continuous monitoring using GIS-based tools is also necessary to detect early signs of salinity intrusion and anthropogenic contamination. The findings of this study provide valuable scientific input for policymakers, water resource managers, and local authorities in designing effective groundwater protection and management strategies for coastal regions experiencing increasing environmental stress.

5 Acknowledgements

The author gratefully acknowledges that this research work forms a part of his doctoral (Ph.D.) study. The authors acknowledge for the use of Geographic Information System (GIS) tools, particularly *ArcGIS 9.1*, which played a significant role in spatial analysis and interpretation of groundwater quality parameters. Authors also thank the laboratory technicians for their assistance in conducting experimental investigations.

6 Author Contributions

Belfin Raj S (Assistant Professor): Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Monisha V (Assistant Professor):** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Data curation. **Dr. Srinivasan K (Research Guide & Associate Professor) & Bebita Robinson Chellathurai (Research Scholar):** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Investigation.

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